

COMBINED CHARACTERIZATION OF THE EFFECTS OF HOT/WET AGING ON A PULTRUDED GFRP PLATE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a combined characterization study of the hot/wet aging effects on a commercially available pultruded Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP). Pultruded GFRPs are being increasingly considered as structural elements in many civil engineering applications. In this work, the performance of a GFRP flat sheet material after exposure to moisture and elevated temperature was interrogated. Samples were immersed in distilled water at 25°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C for a period of 224 days. Moisture absorption measurements on square samples were conducted in order to determine the bulk moisture diffusivity values via the Fickian theory. In addition, the mechanical performance of the aged laminates was assessed in shear. With a view to examining any induced physical change due to hygrothermal aging, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Computed Tomography scanning (CT-scan) were employed on aged and un-aged materials, respectively. Lastly, impedance spectroscopy was used as an innovative supplementary technique to follow hygrothermal aging/moisture absorption during exposure. The combination of characterization techniques was effective in enhancing our understanding on the behaviour of such engineering material when exposed to hot/wet environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

The eagerness for low-cost, high performance and lightweight engineering structures has led to the promotion of Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRPs) composites. In particular, Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer composites (GFRPs) are being increasingly used as structural and non-structural elements in aerospace, civil and naval engineering applications [1]. Due to their nature, they are corrosion-resistant in relatively aggressive environments, i.e. aqueous mediums. To provide confidence in the use of GFRPs, a thorough investigation of the mechanisms which lead to the environmental aging of GFRPs is essential. The hygrothermal performance of such materials has been studied by many researchers [1, 2]. Understanding how moisture affects the durability, and long-term property retention, in aggressive environments has to be a prerequisite before an FRP can be qualified as an engineering material [1, 2].

This paper reports experimental findings of an extensive study on the durability of an ‘off-the-shelf’ GFRP pultruded material as part of the EPSRC funded Duracomp project (EP/K026925/1). The analysis and prognosis of the long-term properties of the materials in a reasonable time-frame was achieved by exposing specimens in hot/wet conditions. The induced degradation was assessed by a complementary study which involved moisture uptake tests, mechanical testing and micrographic examinations such as Computed Tomography (CT-scanning) and Scanning Electron Microscopy

(SEM). Impedance spectroscopy was used as an innovative technique to non-destructively monitor hygrothermal aging.

The characterization work was conducted on a commercially available GFRP flat sheet (FS040.101.096A (1/4"×48"×96" /Series 1500 (I))) supplied by Creative Pultrusions Inc. (<http://www.creativepultrusions.com/>). It consists of a 5-layer polyester matrix laminate reinforced by E-glass fibres rendering a nominal thickness of 6.4mm. Fig.1 displays the structure of the material consisting of three Continuous Strand Mat layers (CSM) with a 33.3% volume fraction of fibres and two UniDirectional (UD) layers with an average 54.5% volume fraction of fibres.

The outer surfaces of the flat sheet are covered by an additional protecting thin and non-structural polyester veil, which has the dual functions of retarding moisture ingress and protecting the GFRP material from UV radiation. It is worth mentioning that after moisture penetrates pass the outermost veil layer it travels in the longitudinal and transverse directions; being faster parallel to the UD fibres. It can be postulated that the veil surface area/edge surface area ratio and the relative magnitudes of the directional diffusion coefficients play a significant role in the moisture uptake characteristics when samples are fully exposed to the aqueous medium.

Figure 1. Construction of the five layered PFRP flat sheet material.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Testing methods

2.1.1 Moisture absorption

For each temperature moisture uptake measurements were conducted over a period of 224 days. Square specimens of $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ were soaked in water and their weight gain was frequently recorded according to ASTM D 5229. The relative moisture change ($M(\%)$) for a sample was determined using Equ. 1:

$$M(\%) = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where M_t is the mass at time t and M_0 the dry initial mass. Prior to immersion in the different water tanks shown in Fig.2a, all samples were oven-dried at 30°C for 48hrs in order to start with complete dryness. For the moisture diffusion coefficient calculation, 2nd Fick's law was employed assuming uniform moisture and temperature conditions inside the material:

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

where x the is the distance along the thickness (h) of the material, C the concentration of the water and D the diffusion coefficient value [3]. Moisture absorption and diffusion processes are functions of temperature, the type of the material, fibre orientation and the fibre volume fraction [4, 5].

Figure 2. Moisture diffusion principle.

Fig.2b illustrates snapshots of the samples employed to characterize the moisture uptake behaviour. As degradation is manifested, increased temperature levels induce changes in the sample's colour indicating potential occurrence of chemical reactions enabled during aging [6]. From Equ.2, according to [3], the solution for the 1D case is:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{D(2k+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{h^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, Equ.3 can be simplified for short and long-term approximations, respectively:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{h^2}} \quad \text{for } Dt/h^2 < 0.04 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \exp\left(\frac{-Dt}{h^2} \pi^2\right) \quad \text{for } Dt/h^2 > 0.04. \quad (5)$$

As long as M_∞ can be determined from a gravimetric curve (see Fig.3), D for a statistically homogeneous material can be determined using the following expression and two points of the moisture uptake M_1 and M_2 at times t_1 and t_2 (Fig.3):

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_\infty}\right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}}\right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{h}{l} + \frac{h}{w}\right)^{-2} \quad (6)$$

where l , w , h represent length, width and thickness of the sample, respectively. In Equ.6 moisture diffusion process is assumed to occur mostly in the thickness direction. The final dimensional parameter in Equ.6 accounts for the contribution in moisture absorption through the (cross-section) edges of the material [7].

Figure 3. Representative of a classical Fickian diffusion three-stage curve for $M(t)$ vs. \sqrt{t} .

2.1.2 Mechanical testing

A series of shear tests were carried out using a 50kN Instron testing machine. Plate twist and iosipescu tests were conducted to estimate the shear modulus (G_{12}) and shear strength (τ_{12}), respectively. In both shear test methodologies, batches of 3 specimens were tested with a constant displacement rate of 1mm/min.

2.1.3 Computed tomography

The internal structure of the un-aged material was examined via a Nikon XT H 225 CT-scanner, allowing for the identification of any intrinsic hidden imperfections i.e. cracks, voids etc. Samples were interrogated with a view to determining the material's structural architecture.

2.1.4 Scanning electron Microscopy

A JEOL SEM6480LV scanning electron microscope was adopted to scrutinize the aging effects on the micro-structure of the material.

2.1.5 Impedance spectroscopy

The dielectric properties of the material were acquired in order to efficiently monitor the hydrothermal aging process of samples soaked at 60°C. Scans were conducted with a Numetric PSM3750 impedance analyzer. Samples of 6x6x15mm³ were prepared and appropriate electrical contacts were applied using silver loaded adhesive paste to fix the electrodes on opposing faces in the through-thickness direction.

2.2 Results and discussion

Fig.4 depicts moisture uptake vs. time curves for all interrogated aging temperatures. As is shown, the rate of moisture uptake elevates with the increase in temperature (Fig.4). In addition, increase in aging temperature leads to increase in the maximum absorbed moisture content ($M(\%)$). Specimens immersed at 80°C have reached moisture maximum after approximately 30 days whereas the rest of specimens reached a moisture content maximum after approximately 150 days of aging.

Figure 4. Moisture uptake vs. time curves for all investigated temperatures.

Temperature	25°C	40°C	60°C	80°C
Diffusion coefficient ($\times 10^{-6} \text{mm}^2/\text{sec}$)	0.47	0.77	1.60	4.25

Table 1. Diffusion coefficient values.

Interestingly enough, the sample aged at 80oC, exhibited a loss in moisture content after reaching a maximum value. This corresponds to mass loss which is likely to have occurred due to chemical decomposition [8]. Table 1 illustrates the diffusivity values for all investigated aging temperatures. As was expected, diffusion coefficient values increase with temperature. This is mainly attributed due to the extra thermal energy that increases the molecular mobility and therefore facilitates the moisture diffusion process.

With respect to mechanical performance (Fig.5), shear properties exhibit a slight decrease in both strength (Fig.5a) and stiffness (Fig.5b) after 112 days of soaking time. This reduction is partially recovered for all examined aging temperatures after 224 days (end of aging regime). It should be noted that shear strength of samples aged at 25°C completely recovered at the end of aging. Additional post-curing occurs which exceeds the effect of structural degradation by the end of the aging regime [2]. As shown in Fig.5, hygrothermal aging at 80oC induced the most significant reductions in shear mechanical properties being the most severe temperature level.

Figure 5. Mechanical testing experimental data.

In Fig.6 a snapshot of the structural architecture of the examined GFRPs is presented. Five samples were interrogated with the CT-scanner at the same time. Cracks (shown in dark colour) located in between the longitudinal fibre reinforcement (bright colour layers) are clearly visible. The generation of the cracks is mainly attributed to the matrix shrinkage after the curing process, and are responsible for the significant moisture transport in the through-thickness direction. Fig.7 depicts a SEM snapshot of a sample aged for 56 days at 80°C. SEM photograph justifies that significant failure in the fibre-matrix interface is inflicted after hygrothermal aging.

Figure 6. CT-scanning image, showing cracks.

Figure 7. SEM image of fibre/matrix interface failure.

Finally, changes of the material's dielectric properties were captured with a view to monitoring the moisture absorption mechanism. Frequency scans were performed in a range of 1Hz to 10MHz. For this test, the specimens were continuously immersed in water at 60°C. Fig.8a depicts the changes of $\tan\delta$ values with aging time as a function of frequency. $\tan\delta$ corresponds to the dielectric dissipation

factor [9, 10]. As is shown in Fig.8a, frequency sweep spectra follow a characteristic trend exhibiting a peak $\tan\delta$ value in the frequency range of $5E-03$ Hz to $1E-04$ Hz. The max $\tan\delta$ values increase with soaking time. To that end, Fig.8b plots the $\tan\delta$ peak-values along with aging time juxtaposed with the actual moisture uptake curve obtained through gravimetric measurements. As it is shown in Fig.8b, the $\tan\delta$ peak-values curve coincides with the moisture uptake curve providing a very promising estimation of moisture absorption behaviour.

Figure 8. (a) $\log(\tan\delta)$ vs. $\log(\text{frequency})$, (b) moisture uptake content (%) and $\tan\delta$ peak values vs. time.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The hygrothermal degradation of pultruded glass fibre reinforced composites was investigated by means of moisture absorption, mechanical degradation, micro-structural assessment and non-destructive monitoring. Samples were hygrothermally aged at elevated temperatures and the coupled effects of moisture and temperature were assessed by a variety of methodologies. It was observed that hot/wet aging accelerates the moisture uptake rate, maximum moisture content, time to saturation and moisture diffusivity. Shear mechanical properties exhibited a complex response to aging initiated by a reductive tendency for 112 soaking days and a characteristic partial recovery at the end of the aging regime. CT-scanning revealed the presence of micro-cracks in the composite structure which is likely to promote the moisture distribution inside the structure. SEM was capable of identifying the presence of fibre/matrix interface failures at aged samples. Lastly, Impedance spectroscopy was effectively used to follow the aging effects with soaking time providing an innovative way to monitor the moisture absorption behaviour.

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